

DEVASAHAYAM AND RANI MARIA

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Abstract: Devasahayam and Rani Maria are among those Jesus-witnesses who by their deeds culminating in the “pouring out of blood” testify to the good news of Jesus Christ. Devasahayam’s boldness and joyful acceptance of persecution as well as Rani Maria’s service for social empowerment and reconciling presence make them paradigms of evangelization. Their boldness corresponds to the *parrhesia* of Jesus and the apostles. As exemplary heralds of Jesus for our times, they inspire us to be courageous and preach the Gospel in such a way that it matches our praxis.

Keywords: Devasahayam, Rani Maria, *Parrhesia*, Courage, Jesus-Witness, Martyrdom.

INTRODUCTION

This series, titled “GOSPEL in ACTION,” sheds light on Jesus’ witnesses who by their deeds culminating in the “pouring out of blood” (cf. Lk 22:20) testify to the good news of Jesus Christ. The twelve Jesus-witnesses introduced in 2026 (February to December 2026) are: Devasahayam, Rani Maria, Herman Rasschaert, John de Britto, Mathew Mannaparambil, James Kottayil, Stan Swamy, Kandhamal martyrs, Arul Doss, AT Thomas, Valsa John, and Tom Gafney. Each of these twelve proclaims the Gospel with a Spirit-guided praxis.

The *Acts of the Apostles* and *When the Gospel Grows Feet*, a biography on Rutilio Grande, inspire the series-title “GOSPEL in ACTION.”¹ In presenting each Jesus-witness, there is (A) a brief introduction to the martyr and his/her contextual Gospel praxis, and (B) a concise exposition to a defining characteristic of witnessing (*martyria*).²

1. DEVASAHAYAM (14 JANUARY): AN EMBOLDENED WITNESS

Devasahayam (23 April 1712 – 14 January 1752), the first Indian lay saint, is a “martyr, fearless herald of the Gospel, and constant witness to the Kingdom of God.”³ Called Nilakandan Pillai until his baptism in 1745, this high royal official continues to distinguish himself in martial arts and linguistic skills. His friendship with Eustace de Lannoy, a centurion of the Dutch army captured and

¹ The title for *Acts* in many Greek manuscripts is *Praxeis Apostolōn*. “The ancient title *Praxeis* was a term designating a specific Greek literary form, a narrative account of the heroic deeds of famous historical or mythological figures.” Cf. Joseph A. Fitzmyer, *The Acts of the Apostles*, Anchor Bible 31 (New York, NY: Doubleday, 1998), 48. The biography of Rutilio Grande, assassinated by Salvadoran army on 17 March 1977 at Aguilares in El Salvador, is by Thomas M. Kelly titled *When the Gospel Grows Feet: Rutilio Grande SJ and the Church of El Salvador - An Ecclesiology in Context* (Collegeville, MN: Liturgical Press, 2013). Both *Acts* and Grande’s biography contain Gospel in praxis, i.e., the good news of Jesus Christ in action.

² In this issue, two martyrs are introduced and the characteristic of *parrhesia* (boldness) lived by both of them is elaborated. It is done so because the January issue was dedicated to the *1700 years of Nicaea*. Sources mentioned in the notes are aimed at further reading to delve deep into the exemplary life and martyrdom of Jesus-witnesses and to assimilate their edifying virtues that inspire our contextual Gospel praxis.

³ Pope Benedict XVI decrees the beatification of Devasahayam and enumerates these qualities in his apostolic letter. Cf. *Acta Apostolicae Sedis* 106/12 (2014): 1067-1069. For biographical sketches of Devasahayam, see J. Kottukapally, *St Devasahayam: Martyr of Modern Travancore* (Mumbai: Better Yourself Books, 2012); John Kulandai E, *Saint Devasahayam: Martyrdom of Devasahayam, a Grace to the Church in India* (Bengaluru: CCBI, 2022); and Sebastian Kizhakkeyil, *Saint Devasahayam: The Holy Martyr of Kattadimalai* (Bengaluru: ATC Publishers, 2022).

made military trainer by the king of Travancore, helps him know about the Gospel and Christian faith. Since then, his spiritual conversations with de Lannoy attracts him further to the unconditional and forgiving love of Jesus Christ, the crucified and risen. “Captivated by the Christian religion,” he expresses “an ardent desire to follow Christ and become a Christian.”⁴ His experience of Jesus Christ and the consequent conversion affirm that “it is not by proselytizing that the Church grows, but by ‘attraction.’”⁵

Devasahayam’s joyful acceptance of afflictions (cf. Acts 5:41) becomes a channel of grace and blessings for others. Testifying to Jesus Christ boldly and doing what Jesus Christ inspires him to do, for example, to break the barriers such as caste that divide, make him pay the price. While labouring for seven months without food, under the scorching sun, rain, or wind, he offers everything to the glory of God. Despite such tortures, his faith in Jesus is never shaken. During his persecution, the local people visit him to receive his blessings and prayers.

A scriptural verse that defines Devasahayam’s witness, highlighted in the decree of canonization, is: “I tell you, my friends, do not fear those who kill the body, and after that can do nothing more” (Lk 12:4; cf. Mt 10:28). Pope Francis reiterates that “these words of the Lord were thoroughly experienced by blessed Lazarus Devasahayam, who never feared to testify his faith before torturers.”⁶ Devasahayam’s boldness makes him a “dreamer of a casteless Indian

⁴ Pope Francis, in his apostolic decree of the canonization of Devasahayam, remarks that “Nilakandan became a close friend of de Lannoy” and he “was eager to embrace Christian faith.” Cf. *Acta Apostolicae Sedis* 115/12 (2023): 1343-1347.

⁵ Cf. Pope Francis, *Evangelii Gaudium*, no. 15. Eustace de Lannoy’s role in Devasahayam’s new life and commitment vouches that “Christians have the duty to proclaim the Gospel without excluding anyone... who point to a horizon of beauty and who invite others to a delicious banquet.” Ibid.

⁶ Cf. *AAS* 115/12 (2023): 1343.

society.”⁷ Dropping the caste tag “Pillai” from the martyr’s name has been deliberate in the decree of canonization. It affirms the strong conviction that the practice of using a caste title as surname must be abrogated. This step taken by a conscientious civil society is based on the baptismal name, i.e., when Nilakandan Pillai chooses Devasahayam (Lazarus) as his name.⁸ It affirms the martyr’s audacity in “preaching the equality of all people at a time and place where caste and religious differences were deep-rooted.”⁹

2. RANI MARIA (25 FEBRUARY): A RECONCILING PRESENCE

Rani Maria (29 January 1954 – 25 February 1995), born as the second child of Eliswa and Paily Vattalil at Pulluvazhy in Kerala, joins the Franciscan Clarist Congregation (FCC) in 1972 and makes her first profession on 1 May 1974. Then, she is missioned to North India in 1975 (Bijnor, Uttar Pradesh). After her final profession on 22 May 1980, she engages in ministry in Satna, Madhya Pradesh (since 1983) and in Indore, Madhya Pradesh (since 1992). Her Hindi learning (1975) and *Harijan* Apostolate Course (1976) at Navjyoti Niketan Pastoral Centre in Patna and her higher

⁷ E. John Kulandai, “Martyr Devasahayam: A Saint for Our Times – Reflections on His Relevance for Today,” *VJTR* 86/4 (April 2022): 258. Kulandai affirms that Devasahayam “died as a witness of the Christian faith that seeks to establish equality of all people by wilfully militating against the injustices of the caste system.” Ibid. Kulandai opines further that “in this era of caste-ridden politics in the society, state and even in the Church, Devasahayam shines out as a saint for social equality, calling us all to build a society devoid of caste and class hierarchy.” Cf. Kulandai, “Devasahayam: Saint of Many Firsts,” *Indian Currents* 34/21 (16-22 May 2022): 10.

⁸ Elsa Lycias Joel describes the efforts of the civil society, especially of Dr. Lazarus Singarayan, a retired scientist of ICAR and professor emeritus of MS University, Tirunelveli, and of Rev. Nazarene Soosai, the Bishop of Kottar, in abrogating the caste surname of the martyr in resonance with the martyr’s own efforts in achieving social equality. Cf. E. L. Joel, “Moved by Christ’s Love,” *Indian Currents* 34/21 (16-22 May 2022): 13.

⁹ Suresh Mathew, “A Saint from the Laity,” *Indian Currents* 34/21 (16-22 May 2022): 3.

education in Sociology from the Rewa University have been helpful in her ministry.¹⁰

Rani Maria is a paradigm of holistic evangelization. She models it, first, on Jesus' own ministry. The Gospel verse, "The Spirit of the Lord is upon me because he has anointed me to bring the Good News to the poor..." (Lk 4:18), that sums up Jesus' mission, orients Rani Maria's life-mission. It leads her to "live and die for the weaker section."¹¹ Jesus Christ shapes her life-mission. Secondly, her response to contextual realities confirms her commitment to the poor. Being "aware of the root causes of poverty," she actively works to break down the "culture of walls" based on caste, creed, class, and ethnicity, building bridges of social friendship and universal fraternity.¹² Thirdly, Rani Maria understands service as a fundamental expression of her faith in Jesus Christ and her love for the poor and the oppressed. It is not merely an act of charity but a core component of her missionary vocation and a way of embodying the Gospel in her daily life.¹³ Rani Maria's legacy as an evangelizer,

¹⁰ These biographic data are extracted from "Appendix 1: A Timeline of the Life of Rani Maria." Cf. Jessy T. Karachira, *Social Witness of a Martyr: The Collected Writings of Rani Maria* (New Delhi: Media House, forthcoming), 389.

¹¹ Cf. Raj Bhujbal, *Sr. Rani Maria: A Martyr for Human Dignity* (Indore: M. P. Voluntary Health Association, 1995), 4. Bhujbal shares that "these words of Jesus Christ were her leading light..." Ibid.

¹² Jessy T. Karachira cites Raj Bhujbal who says that "Sr Rani Maria always gave the topmost priority to providing immediate assistance to the poor, feeding the hungry, sheltering the homeless and clothing the naked. But she was also aware of the root causes of poverty." Cf. Karachira, "Rani Maria's Social Commitment," 151. Thus, Rani Maria's social action has been a creative response followed by an analysis of the pressing needs of her context.

¹³ According to Bishop George Anathil, "Sr. Rani Maria was not just a social worker, but an evangelizer. Her aim was not merely to liberate the people from poverty and exploitation but also to free them from social evils and superstitions through the liberating power of the Gospel." Bincy T. Kottackal, "A Brief Sketch on Sr. Rani Maria Vattalil," in *Rani Maria FCC: Writings with Manuscripts*, ed. Clarence Srambical (Aluva: FCC Generalate, 2013), 9. While conversion was not her "prime aim," she wanted "the poor to experience the values of God's kingdom" and to know and love Christ. Cf. Jessy Thomas

finally, is her reconciliatory role in facilitating her family's forgiveness for Samandar Singh, her assassin.

As “an apostle of forgiveness,” Rani Maria continues to inspire many to forgive and thus to witness to the resurrection of Lord Jesus Christ.¹⁴ The forgiveness-prayer of the proto-martyr Stephen – “Lord, do not hold this sin against them” (7:60) – is inscribed on the monument erected at the spot of the martyrdom of Rani Maria.¹⁵ The documentary *The Heart of a Murderer* and the film *The Face of the Faceless* are tributes to her reconciling presence.¹⁶ These media invite all people of good will to be an “evangelical presence” in accompanying the least and the last and in engaging in people's struggles for justice. Rani Maria's “witness to justice, peace and love... is a worthy homage to the people the Church is called to serve, and a worthy testimony of our faith in Jesus Christ, the martyr who laid down his life for the life of the world.”¹⁷

[Karachira], “Rani Maria, FCC (1954-1995): The Edition of the Writings and the Prayers Collectio: A Source of a Social Spirituality” (PhD diss., Pontificia Universitas Antonianum, Rome, 2023), 417.

¹⁴ Cf. Bincy T. Kottackal, *Rani Maria: Palm of Martyrdom* (Aluva: FCC Publication, 2017), 161. According to Kottackal, Rani Maria “continues to be an apostle of forgiveness even after death. Her forgiving of the killer was a powerful proclamation of Christian faith.” Ibid., 162. At Rani Maria's tomb, Samandar exclaimed that “it is like a sanctuary of peace and strength” and believes that his peace is “a gift from Rani Maria.” Ibid.

¹⁵ Cf. Kottackal, *Rani Maria*, 179. Kottackal affirms that “this [forgiveness] prayer of the proto-martyr, St Stephen, inscribed on the monument erected at the spot of the martyrdom of Rani Maria gives voice to her eloquent silence. No doubt, it is the proclamation of the inner thirst of Rani Maria.” Ibid.

¹⁶ *The Heart of a Murderer*, directed and produced by Catherine McGilvray (2013); *The Face of the Faceless*, directed by Shaison P. Ouseph, produced by Sandra D'Souza Rana (2023).

¹⁷ Cf. S. Arokiasamy, “Editorial,” *VJTR* 62/1 (January 1998): 4. Arokiasamy opines that “Rani Maria and so many others indicate clearly that in its social mission the Church has entered an explosive minefield. The witness to justice, peace and love is costly. It is also a worthy homage to the people the Church is called to serve, and a worthy testimony of our faith in Jesus Christ, the martyr who laid down his life for the life of the world.” Ibid., 4-5.

3. BOLDNESS (*parrhesia*)

The frankness and courage that both Devasahayam and Rani Maria manifest in proclaiming Jesus Christ affirms its source in the Holy Spirit. The Spirit emboldens them to testify to their faith. This boldness corresponds to the *parrhesia* of Jesus and the open and authoritative testimony of the apostles. The post-resurrection community in Jerusalem prays for boldness amidst persecution (Acts 2:29; 4:29). Luke narrates how fearlessly Peter, Stephen, Paul, and others stand before the Jews or the Gentiles and proclaim the works of God.¹⁸ Their boldness is the fruit of the Holy Spirit (4:31). This provokes astonishment (4:13), division (14:3), and persecution (9:27).

In Classical Greek literature, the right for free speech is “the characteristic of a democracy, but there is the danger of misuse, as Plato shows (*Rep.* 8, 557b).”¹⁹ Here *parrhesia* is the mark of someone who is morally free and who does not shun public attention. A good conscience is mentioned as a prerequisite for *parrhesia*. Speaking truth candidly and countering fear is deemed important.

The term *parrhesia* is used in the New Testament, especially in Acts, to denote both speech and a person’s behaviour. To act with *parrhesia* means to act boldly and courageously. This particular theological legitimation of freedom of speech results in the attitude of preachers who proclaim what they hold to be the truth, because they consider

¹⁸ The noun *parrhesia* is used in Acts 2:29; 4:13,29,31; and 28:31. Its verbal form is in Acts 9:27; 13:46; 14:3; 18:26; 19:8; and 26:26. Cf. Hans-Christoph Hahn, “*parrhesia*, Openness, Frankness, Boldness,” in *The New International Dictionary of New Testament Theology*, vol. 2, ed. Colin Brown (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 1976), 736. Heinrich Schlier renders *parrhesia* as “candour” and “to speak with candour or boldness...” and comments that “in Acts the meaning of *parrhesia* is basically controlled by the situation of confession... it is not that of [men] whose training has given them rhetorical ability. Theirs is a different power... The Lord gives such *parrhesia* to his servants.” Schlier, “*parrhesia*,” *TDNT*, 5:882. The Spirit of the Lord emboldens the witnesses.

¹⁹ Hahn, “*parrhesia*,” 2:735.

themselves as having been emboldened by the Spirit and sent by God. The NT shows that *parrhesia*'s field of reference is differentiated, ranging from freedom to say everything to familiarity, courage, frankness, and openness. When Jesus speaks openly to his disciples, he uses a different type of speech from that used by his disciples when they proclaim Christ's message to the world, although in both cases the word *parrhesia* is used. Jesus' *parrhesia* refers to an open and clear mode of speaking, while the disciples' *parrhesia* refers to their ability to preach with confidence and courage.

Just as the Jerusalem community prays not for deliverance from their trials, but that the Lord grant the servants to speak the word with "boldness," Jesus' followers today are in urgent need of the freedom and right to participate fully in public debates over civic matters. It is the right of free speech, *parrhesia* – openness, boldness, and frankness – despite enduring trials, to uphold the truth. Devasahayam and Rani Maria, as bold and exemplary heralds of truth for our times, inspire us that we "speak truth to power" and preach the Gospel in such a way that it matches our praxis.

CONCLUSION

Witnessing to the Gospel of Jesus Christ, Devasahayam and Rani Maria live exemplary lives that culminate in the "pouring out of blood." Devasahayam's boldness and joyful acceptance of persecution inspire us to face contemporary crises. Similarly, Rani Maria's service for social empowerment and reconciling presence offer pathways to building an egalitarian and peaceful society. Their boldness corresponds to the *parrhesia* of Jesus. The courageous and authoritative testimony of the apostles resonate in them. As exemplary heralds of the Gospel, they inspire us that we "speak truth to power" and proclaim the kingdom of God unceasingly (cf. Acts 28:31).